

Approaches towards a platform for exploratory knowledge interaction with connections to the European Dictionary Portal: Austrian Youth Language and Culture

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1. Introduction

Interaction with digital media, e.g. smart phones, social media platforms, etc., have become a common, day-to-day habit for youngsters to communicate with friends and peers. Youth language, i.e. the particular linguistic patterns and features typically used by youngsters, including abbreviations (YOLO), combinations of English words with words from other languages (German: chillaxen) or combinations of numbers and letters (gr8), is thus a widely used way of the young generations to employ their own “code” of communication across different languages and cultures. In addition, symbols such as emoticons or emojis (☺) are increasingly used to express different emotions or to enhance meanings of words or messages, instead of writing and spelling them out. Thus, one of the characteristic features of youth language is its rapidly changing vocabulary, which often varies from year to year, giving rise to new editions of youth language dictionaries (e.g., *Jugendsprache 2017* Langenscheidt; *PONS Wörterbuch der Jugendsprache 2017*) as well as votings and nominations for “youth language term of the year” (*Jugendwort des Jahres*)¹ each year. Moreover, also local regional differences or dialect forms may contribute to word creations (Ziegler & Lenzhofer, 2016).

Even though youth language has been widely studied from linguistic or cultural perspectives, its coverage in the field of Digital Humanities is still relatively little represented. In this paper we introduce a first approach towards creating an interactive platform for youth language and culture, taking a recently collected corpus of Austrian youth language terms as a case study. With the help of lexicographic tools, such as the Viennese Lexicographic Editor (VLE), digital access, editing and archiving is enabled. In addition, the VLE is a tool that can be used for free and which can readily be employed also by other dictionaries. Our collection can thus also be enlarged in the future, linked to relevant external sources or to the European

¹ <http://www.jugendwort.de/abstimmung/>

2. Data and Data Collection

At the outset of this initiative a workshop was held this year at a local Austrian Children's University (Steyr) ("Wie sich die Sprache verändert", 2016). Together with a group of around 20 youths, all between 12-14 years of age, a corpus of currently used youth language terms was collected. First, the youngsters collected general information on the use of youth language such as, for example, by whom it is spoken, in which situations it is typically employed or when youngsters potentially stop using it. Then, they noted recent terms and their meanings (n=125), and also came up with their own, newly invented terms (n=40) that they thought to be relevant for communication. In this way linguistic strategies, but also associated cultural information on how young people name the world and refer to their immediate surroundings were elicited and collected.

3. Digital data processing

As a next step, the corpus of collected terms was digitized using the Viennese Lexicographic Editor (VLE) (c.f. Budin, Moerth & Durco, 2013; Moerth, Procházka & Dallaji, 2014). With the help of this lexicographic tool, digital access and archiving is ensured, but also collaborative editing and future enlargement. In addition, the VLE operates on currently used standards offering TEI compliant annotations for processing lexicographic and terminological data, which makes these data comparable and compatible also with other collections. As a result, the created resource then also offers further possibilities for Citizen Science involvement and addressing of new research questions, which we envisage to elaborate on and implement in a platform for dynamic knowledge interaction on Austrian Youth Culture.

4. Approaches towards dynamic knowledge interaction – outlook and future perspectives

Having initiated a first approach towards creating a collaborative environment, we envisage to give impulse to dynamic knowledge interaction on youth language and culture between researchers and the local youth, taking Austrian youth language as a case study and starting point. A main goal of such an initiative lies in gaining insights on linguistic as well as cultural information of youth language across different regions, but also to provide a platform for youths to actively contribute to and interact with. The resulting platform envisages to offer room for a collaborative Austrian Youth language

² www.dictionaryportal.eu/

dictionary where the youths themselves can contribute to and interact with lexicographic tools (i.e. VLE) in a Digital Humanities context.

As our comprehensive collaborative approach aims to work in close connection with the users, i.e. the local youths, we have already taken the next steps and have applied for further workshops at different local Austrian Children's Universities this year. In addition to collecting more lexicographic and cultural information to have wider regional coverage, we now also aim for workshops where we will specifically integrate the collaborative development of the platform. More concretely, our approach includes the development of open workflows based on the use of the VLE as well as the use of standards (e.g. TEI), already an integral part of the VLE. In addition we also envisage the use of open repositories. By assigning individual ORCids (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)³, for example, for each contributing youngster or pupil, it would be possible to render their work and lexicographic contributions traceable and visible.

Insights resulting from this undertaking can further be shared and included in more wide-ranging infrastructures such as the COST ENeL network on eLexicography⁴, and in this context to the European Dictionary Portal⁵ as far as lexical content is concerned. Ultimately, we plan to expand and open the platform on a wider European level in collaboration with the European Children Universities Network^{6,7}, to youth cultures in other countries, where our example on Austrian youth language serves as a starting point and initial use case.

The platform then will also provide room for collaborative activities that go beyond primarily linguistic and lexicographic endeavours, but towards a more holistic approach to identity and youth culture as such.

5. References

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³ <http://orcid.org/>

⁴ <http://elexicography.eu>

⁵ <http://dictionaryportal.eu>

⁶ <http://kinder.univie.ac.at/en/eucunet.html>

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